

A comparative lexicographical analysis of Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus

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Abstract

The Emperor Marcus Aurelius and the former slave Epictetus represent the social poles of the Roman Empire, yet both are cornerstones of late Stoic thought. This study employs digital humanities tools to investigate how their disparate life experiences and professional roles produced divergent philosophical "signatures" in their extant literature. By analyzing the Lemmatized Ancient Greek Texts (LAGT) corpus, we identify a distinct linguistic polarity: Marcus Aurelius demonstrates a significant preference for physical and cosmological terminology, reflecting a Stoicism centered on the providential order of the universe. Conversely, Epictetus's lexicon shifts toward terms of ethical practice, pedagogy, and the transformation of the moral will. While Marcus Aurelius employs a more poetically diverse and intellectually wide-ranging vocabulary, Epictetus utilizes a more repetitive, concentrated technical vocabulary suited for the classroom. Despite these differences, a high degree of overlap reveals a "common core" of Stoic concepts shared by both authors, such as the nature of impressions and the primacy of the divine. These findings quantitatively highlight the adaptability of Stoicism, illustrating how a robust philosophical core was reframed to serve both the private reflections of a struggling ruler and the public exhortations of a committed teacher.

Introduction

Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus represent two of the most important sources for information about Stoicism and, in particular, the philosophy and beliefs of the later Stoa. From its inception in Athens during the early Hellenistic period, generations of philosophers developed Stoicism into a sophisticated wholistic system comprised of three

interconnected topics—Logic, Physics, and Ethics—supported by a complex and specialized philosophical language (Long 1986; Long & Sedley 1987).

Stoic Logic is essentially dialectical in nature and deals with the so-called "sayables" (λεκτά / *lekta*), which are the underlying meanings or propositional contents of all that we say and think. The Stoics developed a sophisticated propositional logic that anticipates modern systems through the use of logical operators—such as the conditional ("if...then"), the conjunction ("and"), and the disjunction ("or") (Bobzien 2020). While the early Stoics, such as Chrysippus, wrote extensively on Logic, the extant texts of late Stoicism deal with it sparingly. It remains a matter of debate whether this represents a school-wide shift away from Logic or is simply a historical accident regarding which texts survived (Sellars 2006).

Stoic Physics is built on a monistic view of reality where the *cosmos* (κόσμος) is one whole interconnected and consciously rational entity (Long 1986; Sellars 2006). In this pantheistic framework God (θεός / *theos*)—often identified as Zeus (Ζεύς)—is synonymous with Nature (φύσις / *physis*) and the interconnected whole is maintained and evolves/progresses according to divine reason, also referred to as the *logos* (λόγος). Thus, every event, according to this view, is brought about by essentially providential and rational causal chains. The Stoics included a physical model for how the *logos* could act upon inert matter: a substance known as *pneuma* (πνεῦμα), which they conceived of a sort of "rational breath" or "fiery spirit" that permeates reality. This *pneuma* provides the internal tension (τόνος / *tonos*) necessary to give structure, life, and order to the whole (ὅλον / *holon*). Consequently, every event in the Stoic universe is brought about by essentially providential causal chains, leaving no room for true randomness or chaos. For the individual, this means that the human soul (ψυχή / *psuche*) is a fragment of the universal whole, and human reason is a spark of "divine reason" (λόγος / *logos*).

The interconnection posited by Stoic Physics justifies the primary goal of Stoic Ethics: to live in accordance with Nature (κατὰ φύσιν ζῆν). While earlier Stoics developed each aspect of the tripartite system, including extensive work on Logic, it is Ethics that takes up the central focus of later Stoicism (Sellars 2006). In the works of Epictetus, for instance, Logic is utilized as a tool for the "discipline of assent" (συγκατάθεσις), ensuring that the practitioner is not misled by false impressions (φαντασία / *fantasia*). Through this discipline, one can make correct use of their "faculty of choice" (προαίρεσις / *prohairesis*) in evaluating what is truly good (καλός / *kalos*), which in Stoicism is virtue (ἀρετή / *arete*). A fundamental component of this ethical framework is the sharp distinction between what is external—which is not "up to us" (ἐφ' ἡμῖν / *eph' emin*)—and what is internal, which is up to us. Externals, such as health, wealth, or reputation, are classified as "indifferent" (ἀδιάφορος / *adiaphoros*) because they have no inherent bearing on virtue. It is only through the exercise of the faculty of choice in selecting between these

indifferents that moral good (καλός / *kalos*) and moral evil (κακός / *kakos*) come into existence.

To be classified as good, a choice must be true and aligned with Nature. This alignment must occur on multiple scales, reflecting the various roles a human plays within the interconnected whole (τὸ ὅλον): e.g., aligning with our rational and social nature. This social nature of humanity is of paramount importance; the interconnectedness of the cosmos (κόσμος) implies ethical duties not just to Man (ἄνθρωπος / *anthropos*) but to the greatest city (πόλις / *polis*) which is the cosmos itself. By fulfilling these duties and maintaining the integrity of one's faculties, the practitioner achieves freedom from irrational disturbance (ἀπάθεια / *apatheia*) and true flourishing or happiness (εὐδαιμονία / *eudaimonia*).

With this strong emphasis on Ethics and the pivotal role played by Epictetus in transmitting Stoic doctrine to Marcus Aurelius—who likely had access to detailed notes on Epictetus' lectures—one could expect significant concordance between the writings of these two Stoics. This, however, does not take into account the very different stations each man possessed within Roman society, as well as the divergent purposes of their speech and writing. Epictetus was a former slave from the absolute bottom rung of Roman society who became a philosopher and teacher after being freed. Marcus Aurelius was a wealthy patrician groomed from a young age to take up his post as Roman emperor: the absolute highest rung in that society and one of the most powerful figures of antiquity.

Beyond their different social strata, the writings that come down to us reflect very different purposes. The *Meditations* of Marcus Aurelius are a collection of *hypomnemata*: short, fragmented philosophical musings directed at oneself and meant to help internalize particular doctrines. Conversely, the *Enchiridion* and *Discourses* of Epictetus are essentially collections of "lecture notes" from public talks given by the Stoic teacher, collected and edited by a dedicated pupil, Arrian of Nicomedia.

In this way, the primary textual sources for late Stoicism arrive from two rather disparate contexts. Despite their shared philosophical lineage, the vocabulary of Epictetus and Marcus Aurelius likely reflects each man's distinct perspectives and goals. This presents a significant opportunity for the application of the tools of digital humanities to perform lexicographical analyses that can shed light on this potential divergence (Bamman & Crane 2009; McGillivray 2014; Piotrowski 2022). In this study, we have accessed the lemmatized Ancient Greek texts of both authors and subjected them to a series of computational textual analyses. This work reveals significant and interesting divergences in philosophical emphasis for each man, even while situated within a robust, shared framework of Stoic thought. Ultimately, these findings highlight a globally shared Stoicism

that is linguistically polarized between the public exhortations of Epictetus' classroom and the private cosmic and intellectual reflections of Marcus Aurelius.

2. Materials and Methods

Computational tools and environment

Analysis was performed using Python 3.11. High-speed processing of input was handled via Pandas and PyArrow. The Classical Language Toolkit (CLTK) (Johnson et al. 2021) was utilized for secondary part-of-speech (POS) tagging and grammatical filtering via the OdyCy model. All materials needed to recapitulate this work are found in **Supplementary File S1**, which contains needed scripts, a detailed usage README, and a requirements.txt file for installing needed dependencies and packages.

Corpus selection

The primary data for this study was extracted from the Lemmatized Ancient Greek Texts (LAGT) v4.1 dataset (Kaše et al. 2024), which draws from the Perseus Digital Library (Crane 1996; Crane n.d.), the GLAUx corpus, and other high-fidelity sources. This dataset was selected for its advanced lemmatization, leveraging the GLAUx treebank and the GreCy spaCy model to resolve complex Greek inflections into dictionary headwords (lemmata). For dictionary matching, the LSJ Dictionary (JSON v1.0.0) provided English definitions for extracted lemmata (Söderholm 2025).

Data extraction and dictionary mapping

The study utilized the Linked Ancient Greek Text (LAGT) corpus version 4.1 to extract lemmatized data for Epictetus (TLG 0557) and Marcus Aurelius (TLG 0562). We filtered the Parquet-based dataset by document identifiers and flattened the nested structures to calculate word frequencies for each author. To ensure accurate integration with a digitized Liddell-Scott-Jones (LSJ) lexicon, we implemented a normalization pipeline using the Python Unicode data library. All lemmata and dictionary keys were standardized to Normalization Form Canonical Composition (NFC), converted to lowercase, and stripped of whitespace. Additionally, final sigmas were converted to medial sigmas to ensure uniform matching across datasets. The final dataset was exported as a tab-separated values (TSV) file containing each unique lemma, its frequency of occurrence, and its corresponding LSJ definition.

Analysis of lexical richness

To evaluate the richness of vocabulary of the two authors, we calculated several measures of lexical variety from the unfiltered vocabulary datasets. We first established the total number of tokens (N), representing the sum of all word instances, and the number of unique types (V), representing distinct lemmata or dictionary headwords. From these baselines, the Type-Token Ratio (TTR) was calculated as V/R , providing a measure of lexical density; a higher TTR suggests a more varied technical vocabulary, while a lower TTR reflects the repetitive, didactic style common in pedagogical texts (Majumdar 2025).

Because TTR is sensitive to corpus size—typically decreasing as the token count increases—we utilized Guiraud's Index (R) (Guiraud 1954) to provide a more robust comparison. Calculated as $R = V \div \sqrt{N}$, this metric compensates for the "length effect" by using the square root of the total tokens, allowing for a standardized assessment of vocabulary richness across corpora of significantly different scales. Finally, we quantified the occurrence of *hapax legomena*, defined as lemmata that appear only once within a specific corpus. Expressed as a percentage of the unique vocabulary ($Hapaxes \div (V \times 100)$), this metric serves as an indicator of lexical idiosyncrasy, highlighting the extent to which an author employs specialized or illustrative terms.

Corpus normalization and calculation of relative frequency difference

To facilitate a meaningful comparison between the two datasets, we normalized the raw frequency counts to account for the significant difference in size between the works of Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus. The total token count for the Marcus Aurelius sub-corpus (12,350 tokens) and the Epictetus sub-corpus (37,289 tokens) served as the basis for this scaling. The relative frequency was calculated for each lemma by dividing the raw frequency by the total word count of the respective author and multiplying the result by a factor of 10,000. This standardization transformed raw counts into a common metric representing occurrences per 10,000 words, allowing for a direct comparison of lexical density regardless of document length (DHRI 2020).

The normalized datasets were integrated using an outer join on the lemma. To ensure data integrity across the combined dataset, lexical definitions from the Liddell-Scott-Jones (LSJ) dictionary were preserved for all terms, regardless of whether they appeared in one or both authors' works. To focus the analysis on philosophically significant vocabulary and reduce statistical noise from rare terms or *hapax legomena*, a filtering threshold was implemented. Following the principle that low-frequency items can skew comparative measures in corpora of unequal size (Kilgarriff 2001), lemmata with a combined relative frequency of less than 1.0 per 10,000 words were excluded from the final analysis. This

threshold ensures that the resulting Δ in relative frequency reflects sustained stylistic or thematic differences rather than idiosyncratic occurrences (Burrows 2002).

A relative frequency value was calculated for each filtered lemma by subtracting the Epictetus relative frequency from the Marcus Aurelius relative frequency. This metric serves as a directional indicator of lexical preference: a positive RF indicates a higher relative usage by Marcus Aurelius, while a negative RF indicates a higher relative usage by Epictetus (**Supplementary File S2**).

Kernel density estimation and overlap analysis

To visualize and quantify the degree of lexical convergence between Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus, we performed a Kernel density estimation (KDE) analysis of their relative frequency distributions (Węglarczyk 2018). The relative frequencies were log-transformed to a base-10 scale to account for the high skew in the data. We calculated the overlap coefficient to provide a single metric representing the area of intersection between the two probability density functions. The overlap coefficient serves as a measure of similarity ranging from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates identical frequency distributions (Vijaymeena & Kavitha 2016). This coefficient was determined by evaluating the KDEs over a standardized range and integrating the minimum intersection of the two curves (Weisstein 1999). This approach allowed us to assess the distributional similarity between the two Stoic authors (**Supplementary File S3**).

Distributional analysis of relative frequency differences

We generated frequency histograms and performed a statistical analysis of the Δ RF values, representing the difference in relative frequencies for each lemma. We calculated the mean, standard deviation, and mean absolute deviation of these differentials to characterize the spread of the data (**Supplementary File S3**).

Data filtering

To focus in on more philosophically meaningful terms, we performed a targeted removal of 15 high-frequency verbs: specifically, the lemmata γίγνομαι (gignomai / become), δέω (deo / bind), δίδωμι (didomi / give), δοκέω (dokeo / seem), δύναμαι (dynamai / be able), ἐθέλω (ethelo / wish), εἰμί (eimi / be), ἔχω (echo / have), λέγω (lego / say), οἶδα (oida / know), ὁράω (horao / see), ποιέω (poieo / make), πράσσω (prasso / do), φέρω (phero / bear), φημί (phemi / say) were excluded from the filtered dataset. These terms represent functional grammatical terms used with high frequency in Greek (Christopher 2014) that could obscure the more philosophically significant vocabulary. Statistical analyses were re-run after this filtering step, which had minor impact on the overall structure of the results

(**Supplementary File S3**), however revised standard deviations (which were lower) were used in to regenerate word clouds.

Lexical visualization

To synthesize the comparative data, weighted “word clouds” were generated representing authorial preference and the shared Stoic core lexicon (Mueller 2020). Unlike standard frequency-based visualizations, our approach utilized a multi-dimensional scaling of size and color intensity to represent both relative frequency and statistical divergence (ΔRF). The corpus was partitioned into three distinct sets based on a threshold of 1 standard deviation (σ). This threshold identifies the “philosophical signatures” of the two authors, with skew (ΔRF) beyond 1σ , and a “shared core” where $|\Delta RF| \leq 1\sigma$. The σ values used for the unfiltered and filtered results were 7.16 and 5.30, respectively.

For the signature clouds, lemma font size was set proportionate to the relative frequency within that author’s respective corpus, while color intensity was mapped to the magnitude of the ΔRF to highlight the degree of skew toward either philosopher (red for Marcus Aurelius or blue for Epictetus). Conversely, the shared “Stoic Core” (gold) utilized a font size determined by the total relative frequency across both authors, with color shading inversely proportionate to the ΔRF to emphasize the most stable, shared terms. To ensure accurate rendering of the lemmatized Greek headwords, we employed a Unicode-compliant font and generated the visualizations in PDF format to preserve vector-grade legibility for both unfiltered and verb-filtered datasets.

Thematic aggregation and visualization

To assess the broader philosophical emphasis of each author, we selected the 100 highest total relative frequency lemmata (post-filtering) and identified their corresponding morphological stems. Using these stems, we performed a “key words in context” analysis to extract all sentences containing these root concepts from the complete Greek corpora of Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus. To conduct the Key Word in Context (KWIC) analysis, we utilized a custom Python-based harvester designed to extract sentences from the Stoic corpus based on a curated list of high-frequency linguistic stems. This approach was utilized to ensure the inclusion of various inflected and derived forms of key philosophical terms, which might otherwise be omitted by a strict lemma-only search.

Each of the resulting 5371 sentences was submitted to the Gemma-3-27b-it generative AI model. The model was tasked with: (1) translating the Greek sentence into English, and (2) performing a classification “tagging” of the sentence with the most relevant Stoic topos—Logic, Physics, or Ethics—as defined by Hadot (Hadot 1998). Results were then

visualized using an overlapped bar chart to highlight overall thematic emphasis and differences between the two Stoics. The resulting data are in **Supplementary File S4**.

Data and Code Availability

All primary linguistic data utilized in this study were derived from open-access repositories, specifically the LAGT corpus v4.1 and the LSJ JSON dictionary. All custom Python scripts and the intermediate comparative datasets (TSV/CSV) required to reproduce these results are provided in **Supplementary File S1** which includes detailed README and requirements files to facilitate reproduction of the results. The complete dataset of 5371 AI-thematic classifications, including original Greek and natural language translations, is provided in **Supplementary File S4**.

Results

Lexical analysis reveals richer vocabulary use by Marcus Aurelius

The corpus of Stoic literature contributed by Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus was accessed from the Lemmatized Ancient Greek Texts (LAGT) v4.1 dataset. This corpus comprises 3223 unique lemmata from Marcus Aurelius and 4671 for Epictetus, reflecting the larger body of extant work for Epictetus (**Supplementary File S2**). An analysis was conducted to evaluate the richness and diversity of vocabulary in each corpus (**Table 1**). This analysis reveals distinct profiles between the two Stoic authors. Marcus Aurelius demonstrates a high degree of lexical diversity with a Type-Token Ratio (TTR) that is more than double that of Epictetus. While the observed differences in TTR could be due to different corpus sizes, the size-normalized Giraud's index is also larger for Marcus.

Notably, the raw count of Hapax Legomena (isolated singly appearing terms) is nearly equivalent between the two authors despite Epictetus' corpus being approximately three times larger than that of Marcus Aurelius. This disparity is most evident in the Hapax %: while Epictetus's unique word usage is relatively constrained at 40.29%, over half of the lemmata in the *Meditations* (57.09%) appear only once. This suggests that while Epictetus relies on a concentrated technical vocabulary, Marcus employs a more poetically rich and diverse lexicon.

These results are complemented by the calculation and plotting of the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) of the relative frequency (**Supplementary File S3**). Here there is a large high-density peak toward the lower frequency lemma range for the Marcus distribution that represents his more diverse word use. Despite these distinct features, there is notable overlap between the two datasets, as evidenced by a calculated overlap coefficient of 0.77.

Analysis of differential word use reveals distinct authorial signatures

To have a normalized metric to make comparisons, relative frequencies (RF) for each lemma were calculated as occurrences per 10000 words (**Supplementary File S2**). Further, a relative frequency Delta (Δ RF) was calculated by taking the difference in RF between each lemma in Marcus Aurelius' vs. Epictetus' work. To assess the distribution of lemma RF values, a histogram was generated (**Supplementary File S3**). The distribution is centered around a mean Δ RF of 0.00 with a standard deviation (σ) of 7.16 and a mean absolute difference (MAD) of 2.88. This tight distribution centered on zero aligns with the results of the previous section, highlighting a robust core Stoic vocabulary.

To reveal distinct authorial signatures indicated by the previous results, a frequency-vs-difference analysis was visualized using a two-dimensional scatter (volcano) plot distribution (**Fig. 1**). Movement along the Y-axis represents the prevalence across both datasets (total RF). Words that are high on the plot are the high-frequency backbone structural words of the corpus: e.g., λόγος (*logos* / [divine] reason) and φύσις (*physis* / Nature). Words lower on the axis are relatively rare, but potentially philosophically significant words that represent the more specialized vocabulary of Stoicism: e.g., προσοχή (*prosoché* / attention) and συγκατάθεσις (*synkatathesis* / assent).

Movement along the X-axis represents the lexical divergence—the difference in relative frequencies (Δ RF) of words used by Marcus Aurelius vs. Epictetus (**Fig. 1**). Words toward the center are the core of shared language/concepts of their Stoic philosophy. Movement toward the negative shows an increasingly dominant Epictetus signature and toward the positive a more Marcus Aurelius dominant signature. Inspection of the upper-most quadrants at both extrema gives a picture of the unique lexical signature of each philosopher.

Visualization of lexical divergence and the common Stoic core

To qualitatively visualize skews in word use, as well as identify the common core of stoic vocabulary, we generated word clouds weighted by skew in relative frequency usage and overall prevalence (**Fig. 2**). Highly prominent (high skew, high Δ RF) words in the Marcus Aurelius corpus are φύσις (*physis* / Nature), ὅλος (*holos* / *the whole*), ποιέω (*poieo*, make or create) and γίγνομαι (*gignomai* / become or come into being). After filtering out high relative frequency verbs, the words φύσις and ὅλος are still prominent, but now other philosophically important terms such as κόσμος (*cosmos* / universe), λόγος (*logos* / [universal] reason), ψυχή (*psyche* / conscious self [psyche]), ἄνθρωπος (*anthropos* / mankind), and βίος (*bios* / life) appear more prominently.

Epictetus heavily favors verbs like by εἰμί (*eimi* / be), λέγω (*lego* / say), ἔχω (*echo* / have), ἐθέλω (*ethelo* / want or wish), and δέω (*deo* / bind). After filtering out these, and other, high-frequency Greek verbs, prominent terms include μέγας (*megas* / great or big), πολὺς (*polus* / many), ἔρχομαι (*erxomai* / go), φιλόσοφος (*philosophos* / lover of wisdom

[philosopher]), καλός (*kalos* / good) ἔργον (*ergon* / deed or action) and ἀκούω (*akouo* / listen or pay attention).

The “Core Stoic” words that are heavily used by both Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus (high prevalence and low skew) are words like κακός (*kakos* / bad or evil), ἀγαθός (*agathos* / good), θεός (*theos* / God), and φαντασία (*fantasia* / impression or appearance) which all remain prominent after filtering common verbs.

Thematic profile analysis finds distinct differences in focus

While the qualitative trends observed in the previous results are intriguing, the description of key themes from relative frequency alone suffers from context dependence of the word usage: i.e., individual lemma thematic meaning depends on their context of usage in the broader text. To address this, we performed a “key word in context” analysis of the top 100 highest total relative frequency lemmata across the work of Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus. Using the stems of each lemma we searched the complete texts of each Stoic to extract 5371 full sentences (1389 from Marcus Aurelius and 3982 from Epictetus). Each sentence was passed to the Gemma-3-27b-it generative AI model for Greek-to-English translation and thematic tagging with one of the three Stoic themes/topics: Logic, Physics, or Ethics, with an explanation of the decision (**Supplementary File S4**).

To compare the thematic emphasis between each author the resulting sentence frequencies were aggregated for each of the three Stoic themes/topics and normalized as percentages of total pulled sentences for each Stoic. The results show the strong emphasis placed on Ethics by both Stoics (**Fig. 3**); however, there is a skew in emphasis given on Ethics vs. Physics for each Stoic. Of the sentences pulled for Epictetus, 89.98% are most closely related to Ethics, while Logic and Physics are rarely covered: 3.19% and 6.83%, respectively. For Marcus Aurelius, Ethics is also a dominating theme, but to a much lesser extent than Epictetus—accounting for only 77.75% of pulled sentences. The difference can be accounted for by his much heavier emphasis for Physics, which comprised 20.30% of pulled sentences. Like Epictetus, Marcus only covered Logic minimally, with 1.94% of pulled sentences being tagged with this theme.

Focused analysis of key Stoic technical terminology highlights differences

A set of key Stoic technical terms were extracted from the main dataset (**Supplementary File S2**) to facilitate a more focused and granular analysis of differences. These were organized into three tiers based on their authorial skew (cutoffs defined by the standard deviation) (**Table 2**). Consistent with the broader thematic findings, the Marcus Aurelius Signature group is dominated by Physics-associated and cosmological terms. The most dramatic differences are seen in φύσις (*physis* / Nature), ὅλος (*holos* / The Whole),

and κόσμος (*kosmos* / Universe). These terms are used 3 to 6 times more frequently in the *Meditations* than in Epictetus' work.

In contrast the Epictetus Signature group exhibits a focus on ethical practice and the evaluation of impressions. Most notably, προαίρεσις (*prohairesis* / faculty of choice) and καλός (*kalos* / good) show strong skews toward his corpus. His preferential use of *prohairesis* is nearly 28 times that of Marcus, underscoring the importance of this discipline to Epictetus' philosophy.

The shared Core Stoic terms have notably similar relative frequencies ($|\Delta RF| < 5.30$). Terms like θεός (*theos* / God), κακός (*kakos* / evil), and φαντασία (*fantasia* / impression) are used with almost identical relative frequency by both authors underscoring the fundamental importance of the divine and the nature of impressions to their shared Stoic Philosophy. A nuance should be noted for several highly specialized terms within this core. While the ΔRF values for the terms συγκατάθεσις (*synkatathesis* / assent), ἀπάθεια (*apatheia* / freedom from [disturbing] emotion), and εὐδαιμονία (*eudaimonia* / happiness) are small, the relative frequency of their usage by Marcus Aurelius is extremely low (0.81) (**Supplementary File S2**). Conversely, the term πνεῦμα (*pneuma* / breath or spirit) is used very rarely by Epictetus (0.54). Even within the specialized vocabulary of the Core Stoic terms, we see some evidence of thematic bias by the near absence of usage of these terms by either author: Epictetus is more prone to using terms associated with volition and practice, while Marcus uses a term associated with cosmology.

Discussion

The physical and cosmological focus of Marcus Aurelius

One of the most striking findings of this study is quantitative support for scholarship that emphasizes the physical/cosmological orientation of Marcus Aurelius' Stoicism (Gill 2006; Gill 2013). For example, Pierre Hadot in his seminal work on the philosophy of Marcus Aurelius identified “the view from above” (a spiritual exercise to reframe one's perspective to reflect a cosmic viewpoint) as a central motif (Hadot 1998), which has also been enriched by subsequent scholarship (Gill 2006). The dominance of terms like φύσις (*physis* / Nature), ὅλος (*holos* / the whole), λόγος (*logos* / reason), and κόσμος (*cosmos* / universe) in the *Meditations* (**Fig. 2** and **Table 2**) highlights this tendency toward the cosmic. More quantitatively, in our thematic analysis (**Fig. 3**) there is a clear skew towards the Stoic topic of Physics. 20.30% of all the analyzed sentences from the *Meditations* were tagged as being most related to Physics, vs. only 6.83% of analyzed sentences from Epictetus. In contrast, while Ethics was a dominating theme for both Stoics, there is a

clear preference in the work of Epictetus: with 89.98% of analyzed sentences being related to Ethics vs. 77.75% for Marcus Aurelius.

One could speculate that for Marcus Aurelius, the emperor of Rome, this orientation toward Physics/cosmology—the *logos* as the providential ordering principle of the cosmos—was a powerful psychological consolation (Gill 2013). As his rational mind was put to the ordering of the Roman state, the *logos*/God ordered the whole (Sellars 2006; Sellars 2013). Furthermore, through the lens of this cosmic perspective, his private and professional thoughts and actions take on particular importance, as they are reflections of an ordered whole: i.e., by working toward justice/order in the state, he is also participating in the order/justice of the “greater city” which is the cosmos.

It should be noted here that the assignment and comparison of thematic tags is potentially challenging. The term like φύσις (*physis* / Nature) and its extremely high density of use on the work of Marcus Aurelius (**Fig. 1** and **Fig. 2**) is itself a strong indication of the physical and cosmological focus of Marcus Aurelius (indeed this is the root of the English word physics); however, φύσις may occur in the context of an entire sentence that, on the whole, may be classified in a different theme. Looking at the results of the thematic analysis, of the 218 sentences that contain φύσις, 208 are tagged with Ethics, 10 are tagged with Physics, and 0 are tagged with Logic (**Supplementary File S4**).

The intellectual focus of Marcus Aurelius

Another interesting result of this study is the higher TTR and Giraud index for Marcus' work (**Table 1**), as these metrics quantify the poetic and diverse word usage found within the wide-ranging intellectual focus of his private *hypomnemata* (Rutherford 1991). These lexical richness scores reveal how he engaged with themes such as Physics and Ethics. In the *Meditations*, Marcus often approaches a single philosophical idea from multiple linguistic angles, utilizing a diverse and poetic array of synonyms and imagery (Rutherford 1991). This more literary style results in a more diverse vocabulary and a higher number of unique lemmas.

This emphasis on diverse word usage in the writing of Marcus Aurelius is striking and points to a man working to gain an intellectual understanding of Stoic philosophy. This reflects a preoccupation with topics such as internal governing part of the psyche (ἡγεμονικός), that is explored through terms like νόος (*noos* / mind) and διάνοια (*dianoia* / intellectual capacity). Interestingly, this high degree of lexical diversity could also reflect Marcus' connection to the “Second Sophistic,” a literary and cultural movement in Ancient Rome that emphasized the resurrection of “Attic” styles and themes. Overall, these results could paint a picture of the emperor as a “bookish” and intellectual man focused on the

more cerebral (e.g. physical and cosmological) aspects of Stoic philosophy. In a well-known passage in the *Meditations*, 2.2 (Aurelius & Long) Marcus exhorts himself to “throw away thy books; no longer distract thyself,” perhaps recognizing the limitations of intellectual understanding vs. practice of philosophy.

The focus of Epictetus on ethical practice

From the thematic analysis of Epictetus’ work, we see reduced emphasis on Logic and Physics and an increased tendency of his writing to focus on Ethics, which accounted for over 89.98% of pulled sentences (**Fig. 3**). This finding is all the more striking when one considers that the stem search of the 100 top lemmata included cosmological and physical terms like φύσις (*physis* / Nature) (**Supplementary File S4**). This result may be an indication of Epictetus’ pedagogical priority, which is the transformation of the moral will (προαίρεσις [*prohairesis*]) rather than the accumulation of theoretical knowledge (Graver 2007; Graver 2025). Epictetus is less focused on the ordering structure of the Universe, but more concerned with the ordering structure of his student’s προαίρεσις (*prohairesis* / faculty of choice)—a term used ~28X more frequently by Epictetus (**Table 2**). This aligns with the scholarship that highlights Epictetus’s stress on volition, and the distinction between what is, and is not, up to us (ἐφ’ ἡμῖν) (Graver 2007; Graver 2025; Long 2004). This skew toward ethical practice is further corroborated by other enriched terms such as μελετάω (*meleto* / study) and γυμνάζω (*gymazo* / train), which are frequently used by Epictetus but utterly absent from the work of Marcus Aurelius (**Supplementary File S2**).

Taken together, the relative emphasis on ethical practice and lack of emphasis on Physics or cosmology in the work of Epictetus, might suggest a certain degree of “anti-intellectualism” in favor of philosophical practice. While Marcus Aurelius uses διάνοια (*dianoia* / intelligence) and νόος (*noos* / mind) to understand the λόγος (*logos*) of the whole, Epictetus favors logical terms like συγκατάθεσις (*synkatathesis* / assent to perceptions) (**Table 2**), which, rather than being used as abstract intellectual concepts, are practical tools for actualizing Stoic ethical disciplines: e.g., the “discipline of assent”.

Epictetus’ orientation away from intellectualism is highlighted nicely by a well-known passage from his *Enchiridion*, 49 (Epictetus & Carter):

When anyone shows himself overly confident in ability to understand and interpret the works of Chrysippus, say to yourself, " Unless Chrysippus had written obscurely, this person would have had no subject for his vanity. But what do I desire? To understand nature and follow her. I ask, then, who interprets her, and, finding Chrysippus does, I have

recourse to him. I don't understand his writings. I seek, therefore, one to interpret them." So far there is nothing to value myself upon. And when I find an interpreter, what remains is to make use of his instructions. This alone is the valuable thing. But, if I admire nothing but merely the interpretation, what do I become more than a grammarian instead of a philosopher? Except, indeed, that instead of Homer I interpret Chrysippus. When anyone, therefore, desires me to read Chrysippus to him, I rather blush when I cannot show my actions agreeable and consonant to his discourse.

The common core of Stoic Philosophy

As noted earlier, the overlap coefficient between each philosophical corpus was remarkably high (0.77; **Supplementary File S3**), supporting a robust Stoic lexical core between Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus (Sellars 2013). Despite the observed differences in emphasis between the two philosophers (e.g., the skew towards Physics/cosmology in Marcus' work and the preference for Ethics and practice in Epictetus'), the two Stoics showed great similarity in word usage, evidenced by findings from our visualization of the "core Stoic" word cloud (**Fig. 2**) and the focused analysis of key Stoic terms (**Table 2**). Words with strong ethical connotations, such as κακός (*kakos* / bad or evil) and ἀγαθός (*agathos* / good or admirable) dominate the cloud and are used with equally high frequencies by both philosophers. This similar emphasis given by both men supports the noted importance of Ethics to late Stoicism (Sellars 2006), which is quantitatively indicated in this current study (**Fig. 3**).

It's also important to note that while Marcus Aurelius' word usage is skewed toward the Physics/cosmology theme, Epictetus also uses cosmological terms. Most notably, the cosmological term θεός (*theos* / God) dominates the core Stoic word cloud (**Fig. 2**) and is used with equally high relative frequency by both philosophers (**Table 2**). This highlights the centrality Stoic concept of God/providence, the primacy of virtue (ἀρετή), and a social orientation towards mankind (ἄνθρωπος).

Another key finding of this study is the quantitative support for the widely-noted lack of emphasis on Logic in late Stoicism (Sellars 2006). Both Epictetus and Marcus Aurelius show reduced specific attention to this topic: e.g., Logic was the least frequent thematic tag for the sentences pulled from either Stoic, with 1.94% and 3.19% of sentences pulled for Marcus and Epictetus, respectively (**Fig. 3**). Our results, however, could be used to argue that the late Stoics did not necessarily "abandon" Logic but rather internalized it into Ethics. For example, the term φαντασία (*fantasia* / impressions) is associated with Logic (through the evaluation of impressions), yet in the context of usage is overwhelmingly associated with Ethics. For example, of the 75 sentences pulled 71 were associated with Ethics and only 4 with Logic (**Supplementary File S4**).

The internalization of Logic into the Ethical practice is illustrated nicely by the following translated φαντασία-containing sentence from Epictetus: “τοῦτο δ’ ἐστὶ θνητὸν ζῶον χρηστικὸν φαντασίαις λογικῶς,” which the AI translates as “This is a mortal animal benefiting from impressions reasoned through logically.” Although the AI tags this as “Ethics” due to its focus on virtuous living and inner peace, the presence of the adverb λογικῶς (logically) reveals the underlying logical roots of this Ethics focused passage. In this example, subsuming logic into the 'discipline of assent,' Epictetus utilizes Logic as tool for improving moral character (e.g., by assenting to true impressions). Thus, the low frequency of 'Logic' in the data does not represent an absence of logical thought, but rather its integration/intermingling with the other topics/themes. These results suggests that for these two late Stoics, Logic was primarily used as an applied ethical methodology.

The linguistic context behind observed polarities

A key factor in the lexical divergence observed between Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus was likely the difference in their intended audiences. The cosmological and literary/intellectual orientation of Marcus Aurelius reflects the private reflections of a man constantly being challenged by external events (Hadot 1998). They consist of repeated reminders of the underlying rationality of the whole (ὅλος / *holos*) and the goodness of acting in agreement with nature. The format of the *hypomnemata* is another potential driving factor, as the redundancy of usage of certain key philosophical terms is a key feature of this format, which was designed as an exercise and aid for internalization of important doctrines. Thus, the high relative frequency terms that emerge in the *Meditations* are related to challenges that the author likely repeatedly faced in his role as Emperor, or intellectual concepts that he struggled to internalize (Gill 2013) or was just intellectually curious about.

In contrast, the orientation of Epictetus toward ethical practice is a potentially a reflection of the dialectical nature of the classroom (Inwood 2022). Both the *Enchiridion* and *Discourses* consist of notes taken from lectures delivered by Epictetus and recorded by his pupil Arrian. These are the exhortations of a Stoic teacher who is seeking to educate and train their students' character. To provide them with the tools to and habits needed to live well/virtuously: e.g., by making the proper use of impressions (φαντασία). This instructive style of speech is reflected in the fact that the most highly skewed words used by Epictetus are all verbs (**Fig. 2** and **Supplementary File S2**), such as λέγω (*lego* / say), ἐθέλω (*ethelo* / want or wish), and δέω (*deo* / bind). Even after filtering for 15 commonly used Greek verbs, ἀκούω (*akouo* / listen or pay attention) is still prominent—emphasizing Epictetus' role as teacher of Stoic practice—thus the bias in his language toward action.

Furthermore, our analyses of lexical diversity (**Table 1**) showed lower type token ratio (TTR) and Giraud index for the corpus of Epictetus' work, which further supports the pedagogical nature of this body of work. The lack of diversity here likely reflects the need for using repetitive presentation styles, phrases, and specialized vocabulary in public lectures. This could also explain the notable prevalence of the words μέγας (*meγas* / great or big), πολὺς (*polus* / many) in the filtered corpus (**Fig. 2**), which may reflect the rhetorical style used by Epictetus to discuss ethical practice. He uses terms of magnitude to contrast the "greatness" of moral freedom with the "smallness" of external things in his "if...then" dialectical style—referring to the "many" distractions or the "great" effort required to maintain one's προσοχή (*prosoché* / attention) and προαίρεσις (*prohairesis* / faculty of choice), which are two Stoic technical terms heavily favored by Epictetus. While both authors used φαντασία (*fantasia* / impressions) frequently, Epictetus's greater emphasis on συγκατάθεσις (*synkatathesis* / assent) in **Table 2** points to the instructional nature of his lectures, where he guides his students in the evaluation of impressions.

The reasoning for the origins of the observed lexical differences between the two Stoics is reinforced by the analysis of the Hapax % (**Table 1**). Specifically, the statistically higher Hapax % for Marcus (57.09%) provides empirical evidence for the literary complexity of Marcus Aurelius' *hypomnemata*. Unlike the public lectures of Epictetus, which show a lower percentage of unique terms (40.29%), likely due to the repetitive and pedagogical nature of classroom speech, Marcus's private reflections are marked by a diverse array of poetic imagery. The high frequency of hapax legomena suggests that Marcus was actively working out his personal Stoic philosophy using a sophisticated and non-repetitive vocabulary. He was an intellectually oriented individual exploring philosophical challenges through a highly sophisticated style of writing that is quite distinct from the classroom speech of Epictetus.

Limitations

While the results presented here are robustly supported and aligned with scholarly intuition, it is important to acknowledge limitations. While the corpus of work from Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus represent the most complete body of late Stoic literature, many other works were lost or come down as fragments (Seddon n.d.). Even for Epictetus, the *Discourses* only contain a sub-set of the books originally recorded and published by Arrian. Moreover, the "double authorship" of the *Enchiridion* and *Discourses* introduced an additional confounding variable: the observed focus on Stoic practice might reflect Arrian's editorial selection rather than the full scope of Epictetus's original Stoic program (Graver 2025). As noted by Sellars, and other scholars, it is not clear that the perceived lack of interest in logic by the late Stoics is a *bona fide* shift or simply the manifestation of a selection bias in the surviving literature (Sellars 2006). Future stylistometric studies

comparing the *Discourses* with Arrian's solo historical works could help isolate an "Arrian signature" that may be used to better define an "Epictetian signature" through comparison.

Another limitation is that the Stoic topic thematic tagging is presents a challenge, as each topic/theme can be convoluted with the others in the context of larger sentences and passages. The convolution of terms and themes ultimately highlights the high amount of integration within the Stoic system, which was emphasized in antiquity using analogies such as an egg: with Logic as the shell, Physics as the yolk, and Ethics as the white (Sellars 2006)—the white and the yolk are distinct but part of one biological unit. Regardless, the gross thematic trends reported here (**Fig. 3**) are robustly supported by the analysis of 5371 sentences containing high relative frequency words (**Supplementary File S4**). Furthermore, these thematic shifts align with the qualitative assessment of observed differences in relative frequencies of terms between Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus (**Fig. 1** and **Fig. 2**), where Physics/cosmology terms are favored by Marcus and Ethics/practice terms are favored by Epictetus (**Table 2**).

Conclusion

The comparative lexicographical analysis of Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus provides quantitative evidence for better understanding the unique emphases of each Stoic. Our data reveals that the work of Marcus Aurelius exhibits a skew toward physical and cosmological themes, while Epictetus's word use is oriented toward ethical practice and instruction. These distinct philosophical signatures likely reflect the distinct social roles and goals of each author. For the emperor Marcus, Stoic Physics provided a cosmologically focused psychological/spiritual consolation that reframed imperial burdens within a rational and providential whole. For Epictetus, the more personalized and instructional focus served as a pedagogical tool for training students in applied Stoic ethical philosophy.

By employing the tools of digital humanities, this study complements existing scholarship by providing empirical backing for the diverse orientations of Stoicism. Stoicism was not a rigid system but a flexible philosophy capable of addressing both the private reflections and exercises of an emperor, as well as the public exhortations of a former slave turned teacher

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Tables

Table 1. Statistical analysis of lexical richness

	Marcus	Epictetus
Tokens (N)	12350	37289
Types (V)	3223	4671
TTR	0.261	0.1253
Guiraud Index	29.00	24.19
Haraxes	1840	1882
Harax %	57.09	40.29

Table 2. Analysis of key Stoic terminology

Lemma	Transliteration	Definition	Marcus RF	Epictetus RF	ΔRF
Marcus Signature:					
φύσις	<i>physis</i>	Nature	148.18	52.83	95.35
ὅλος	<i>holos</i>	Whole	102.83	18.77	84.06
κόσμος	<i>kosmos</i>	Universe	56.68	8.85	47.83
ἡγεμονικός	<i>hegemonikos</i>	Capable of command	36.44	6.97	43.41
ψυχή	<i>psuche</i>	Soul / Conscious self	56.68	21.19	35.49
λόγος	<i>logos</i>	Reason / Creative reason	68.02	45.59	22.43
ἄνθρωπος	<i>anthropos</i>	Mankind	112.55	98.69	13.86
Core Stoic:					
θεός	<i>theos</i>	God / The Deity	75.30	71.33	3.97
κακός	<i>kakos</i>	Evil / Bad	70.45	68.65	1.79
φαντασία	<i>fantasia</i>	Impression / Appearance	31.58	30.84	0.74
πόλις	<i>polis</i>	City / Community	20.24	14.48	5.76
ἀρετή	<i>arete</i>	Excellence (virtue)	12.96	10.46	2.50
ἀδιάφορος	<i>adiaphoros</i>	Indifferent	4.86	4.83	0.03
εὐδαιμονία	<i>eudaimonia</i>	Full happiness	0.81	4.29	-3.48
πνεῦμα	<i>pneuma</i>	Breath / Spirit	3.24	0.54	2.70
ἀπάθεια	<i>apatheia</i>	Freedom from emotion	0.81	2.95	-2.14
συγκατάθεσις	<i>synkatathesis</i>	Assent to perceptions	0.81	2.15	-1.34

Epictetus Signature:

Figure 2. Comparative Word Clouds. Word clouds for the unfiltered (top) and highly used verb filtered data (bottom). The magnitude of the size and shading of the lemma is proportionate the ΔRF for the Epictetus and Marcus signatures, highlighting the skew toward either philosopher (in blue and red, respectively). The central “Core Stoic” word cloud is scored based on the total relative frequency of the lemma and its similar usage (low ΔRF) between Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus (in gold shading).

Thematic Comparison: The Stoic Tripartite Division

Figure 3. Thematic Comparison: The Stoic Tripartite Division. Overlapped bar chart illustrating the comparative relative frequency of the three major Stoic topoi (Logic, Physics, and Ethics) within the writing of Marcus Aurelius (red) and Epictetus (blue). Data represent the classification of 5371 sentences harvested—via morphological stems—of the 100 highest relative frequency lemmata. Each bar represents the percentage of an author’s total analyzed sentences classified into a specific category. The overlapping bars facilitate a direct comparison of the internal thematic emphasis of each philosopher's thought.

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary File S1: A compressed archive containing the complete Python 3.11 computational pipeline. It includes scripts for data acquisition from the LAGT corpus and LSJ dictionary, statistical normalization, visualization generation, and the Gemma-3 AI integration workflow. A detailed README and requirements.txt are included for full technical reproducibility.

Supplementary File S2: A tab-separated variable (TSV) file, "stoic_master_comparison.tsv", containing the comprehensive lexical comparison between Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus. This includes unique lemmata, raw and normalized relative frequencies, delta-RF values, and standardized LSJ definitions.

Supplementary File S3: A document containing supplemental statistical visualizations, including Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) overlap plots with annotated coefficients and delta-RF histograms showing mean, standard deviation, and mean absolute deviation for both unfiltered and filtered datasets.

Supplementary File S4: A comprehensive CSV file containing the thematic analysis for 5371 sentences. Each entry provides the original Greek text, a natural language English translation, the target philosophical stem, and the categorical thematic tag (Logic, Physics, or Ethics) with the qualitative rationale provided by the Gemma-3-27b-it model.

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